

“PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR CLASSIFICATIONS”

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Abstract: The main purpose of this article is to consider the study of Phraseological Units and their types in English, social linguistic features of idioms, lingua cultural aspects, the functional semantic classification of idioms expressing different relationships. Also, the used information in the research about the different classifications of Phraseological units can be used to write theoretical course book on idioms.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi-frazeologik birliklar va ularning turlarini ingliz tilida o'rganishni, iboralarning ijtimoiy lingvistik xususiyatlarini, lissoniy madaniy jihatlarini, turli xil munosabatlarini ifoda etuvchi iboralarning funksional semantik tasnifini ko'rib chiqish. Shuningdek fraziologik birlikning turli xil tasnifi to'g'risida olib boriladigan tatqiqotlarda ishlatiladigan ma'lumotlar- iboralar bo'yich nazariy kurslar kitobini yozish uchun ishlatilish mumkin.

Keywords: Phraseological units, Phraseological fusions, Phraseological collocations, communicative phraseological units, Nominative phraseological units, Interjection phraseological unit

Kalit so'zlar: Frazeologik birliklar, frazeologik birikma, frazeologik kollokatsiya, kommunikativ frazeologik birliklar, nominative frazeologik birliklar, kesma frazeologik birlik

Phraseological unities are partially non - motivated as their meaning can usually be perceived through the metaphoric meaning of the whole phraseological unit. For example, to show one' s teeth, to wash one' s dirty linen in public if interpreted as

semantically motivated through the combined lexical meaning of the component words would naturally lead one to understand these in their literal meaning.

Phraseological unities are much more numerous. They are partially motivated word-groups because their meaning can be usually guessed from the meaning of its components through the metaphorical meaning of the whole phraseological unit. The classification of phraseological units on a semantic principle was suggested by the prominent Russian scholar V.V.Vinogradov, who made the great contribution to this branch of linguistic science. He took into account the degree of idiomaticity (motivation of meaning) of phraseological units that is the relationship existing between the meaning of the whole and the meaning of their component parts. In other words, he considered the degree of semantic cohesion between the components of phraseological units: the more distant the meaning of a phraseological unit from the current meaning of its constituent parts, the greater is its degree of semantic cohesion. Thus, according to this principle Academician Vinogradov V.V. pointed out three types of phraseological units, namely phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological collocations.

Phraseological fusions are completely non-motivated word groups. The meaning of the whole in phraseological fusions cannot be deduced at least synchronically from the meanings of its constituent parts. So, the degree of motivation is very low in this case, and idiomaticity is, as a rule, combined with complete stability of the lexical components and the grammatical structure of the fusion. Phraseological fusions are specific for every language and do not lend themselves to literal translation into other languages. We may give the following examples of phraseological fusions:

- A red tape - bureaucratic methods
- A heavy father - serious or solemn part in a theatrical play
- To kick the bucket - to die

Phraseological unities are much more numerous. They are partially motivated word-groups because their meaning can be usually guessed from the meaning of its components through the metaphorical meaning of the whole phraseological unit. It is important to underline that the metaphorical meaning

is the meaning the word-group acquires as a result of a complete or partial change of meaning of an initial word-combination on the basis of likening of one object of reality to another. Phraseological unities are as a rule marked by a comparatively high degree of stability of the lexical components. The examples of phraseological unities are:

- to add oil to the fire - to make things worse;
- a dark horse - somebody who is secretive or unusually reserved;
- to bend the knee - to submit to a stronger force, to obey submissively;

Phraseological collocations are fully motivated word-groups their meanings are easily deduced from meanings of their constituents. Phraseological collocations are not only motivated but contain one component used in its direct meaning, while the other is used metaphorically. The following phrases illustrate the examples of phraseological collocations:

- To come to power, to make it a rule, to take one's seat, to meet the requirements, to attain success.

The Kunin's classification is the latest outstanding achievement in the Russian theory of phraseology. The classification is based on the combined structural - semantic principle and it also considers the quotient of stability of phraseological units.

1. Nominative phraseological units - are represented by word groups, including the ones with one meaningful word, and coordinative phrases of the type "wear and tear", "well and good".

2. Nominative - communicative phraseological units - include word - groups, of the type "to break the ice" - "the ice is broken", that is, verbal word - groups which are transformed into a sentence when the verb is used in the Passive voice.

3. Phraseological units - which are neither nominative nor communicative, include interjectional word- groups.

4. Communicative phraseological units - are represented by proverbs and sayings. The proverb "An hour in the morning is worthy two in the evening", Never say "Never" Sayings, unlike proverb, are not evaluative and didactic.

5. Interjection phraseological unit- express the people's emotions and feelings and attitudes to the other things, for example: "Good God!", "God damn it".

To sum up, We pointed out the essence of phraseological units. Phraseological units are habitually defined as non motivated word - groups that cannot be freely made up in speech but are reproduced as ready - made units. This term habitually used by linguistics is very often treated as synonymous with the term idiom. Phraseological units can be classified according to different classifications and play an important role in an English language..

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